

D7.1

Communication & Dissemination Plan

Due date of submission: 30/06/2024

Actual submission date: 30/06/2024

Funded by
the European Union

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of contents.....	2
List of figures	3
List of tables.....	3
List of acronyms.....	4
Project information.....	5
Deliverable details	6
Executive summary	7
1 Introduction.....	7
1.1 Context of WP7	7
1.2 Objectives	8
1.3 Management of Communication and Dissemination Activities	8
1.3.1 Coordination and Implementation Procedures.....	8
1.3.2 Tracking and Monitoring Partner Activities	9
2 Target Audience.....	9
3 Key Messages.....	10
4 Dissemination Strategy	11
4.1 I. Open-access scientific publications:	13
5 Tools and channels.....	13
5.1 Project Identity	15
5.2 Project Website	17
5.3 Content Management System	18
5.4 Social Media.....	19
5.5 Printed and Digital Materials	20
5.6 Newsletters	23
5.7 Press Releases	23
5.8 Scientific Publications	24
5.9 Participation in Conferences, Workshops, and Events.....	24
5.10 Stakeholder Engagement.....	24
6 Indicators and Targets	24
7 Levels of Communication & Dissemination.....	24

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

7.1	European Level – European Commission	24
7.2	International Level – Industry, Scientific Community.....	25
8	Methodology.....	25
8.1	Internal Communication	25
8.2	External Communication	25
9	Timeline: Actions in M1 – M6	25
9.1	Project identity and Materials.....	26
9.2	Press Release.....	26
9.3	Website.....	27
9.4	Social Media.....	27
9.5	Newsletter.....	28
9.6	Events Attended.....	28
9.7	Interaction with other EU Initiatives.....	28

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.	European flag and funding statement	14
Figure 2.	LCA4Bio Brand guidelines	15
Figure 3.	LCA4Bio project website	17
Figure 4.	LCA4Bio project poster	20
Figure 5.	LCA4Bio project factsheet	21
Figure 6.	LCA4Bio project brochure.....	22
Figure 7.	LCA4Bio project Word Template.....	25
Figure 8.	LCA4Bio project first press release	26
Figure 9.	LCA4Bio project Social Media followers overview (April 2023).....	27

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1.	Target groups for LCA4Bio results	9
Table 2.	Key Messages for LCA4Bio project	10
Table 3.	Dissemination activities of LCA4Bio	11
Table 4.	Social Media Profiles of LCA4Bio	11

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronyms and abbreviations	Description
BBI JU	Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EPLCA	European Platform on Life Cycle Assessment UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative
LCA	Life cycle assessment
JRC	Joint Research Centre
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PM	Policy Makers
R&I	Research and Innovation
SC	Scientific Community
WP	Work Package
KOM	Kick-Off Meeting
PR	Press Release
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project full title: Harmonised Life Cycle Assessment methods for sustainable and circular

BIO based systems

Acronym: LCA4BIO

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

Topic: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-04 - Environmental sustainability and circularity criteria for industrial bio-based systems

Start date: 1st January 2024

Duration: 36 months

List of participants:

PARTNER N°	PARTICIPANT ORGANIZATION	ACRONYM
1 (Coord.)	CONTACTICA SL	CTA
2	AALBORG UNIVERSITET	AAU
3	LUXEMBOURG INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	LIST
4	INSTITUT NATIONAL DES SCIENCES APPLIQUEES DE TOULOUSE	INSA TOULOUSE
5	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET	NTNU
6	BIOECONOMY FOR CHANGE	B4C
7	BUSINESS E-INCUBATOR GO-UP	GOUP
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCION FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON	CESEFOR
9	SONAE ARAUCO PORTUGAL SA	SONAE
10	ASOCIACION PARA LA CERTIFICACION ESPANOLA FORESTAL	PEFC ESPAÑA

DELIVERABLE DETAILS

Document Number:	D7.1
Document Title:	Initial version of the Communication and dissemination Plan
Dissemination level	PU – Public, fully open
Period:	PR1
WP:	WP7
Task:	T7.1
Author:	Contactica S.L
Abstract:	<p>This document defines the communication and dissemination strategy for the LCA4Bio project, focused on effectively reaching and engaging a wide range of stakeholders, including academic researchers, industry professionals, civil society, and policymakers, among other targeted audiences.</p> <p>This document is dynamic and subject to slight modifications throughout the duration of the LCA4BIO project, if necessary, to ensure the implementation of a tailored strategy aimed at achieving all the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) set at the project's outset.</p>

Version	Date	Description
Version 1	30/06/2024	Initial version
Version 2	21/10/2025	Updates after the Review meeting1

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document outlines the communication and dissemination strategy for the LCA4BIO project, aimed at effectively engaging diverse stakeholders, including academic researchers, industry professionals, civil society representatives, and policymakers, among others. The key components of the strategy are as follows:

- Participation and organization of relevant conferences, workshops, and seminars to present the project's objectives and achievements, and to enhance networking opportunities with potential collaborators and partners.
- Website updates should be done frequently enough such that all stakeholders can stay informed of what is being done at any given time during implementation period.
- Social media platforms together with other online channels should be used extensively while sharing news relating to the project itself or general information related to the LCA4BIO project community.
- Creation of periodic newsletters to engage with various interested audiences and provide concise updates on project activities.
- Development and distribution of accessible and easy-to-understand materials, such as brochures, videos, and fact sheets, to enhance awareness and understanding of the project among non-technical audiences.

Additionally, the project actively seeks partnerships and collaborations with relevant organizations and European projects. LCA4BIO aims to disseminate its activities through participation in various events and institutional relations activities with recognized organizations. Overall, the communication and dissemination strategy of the LCA4BIO project is designed to effectively engage and reach a wide range of stakeholders, and to ensure that the project's results are widely disseminated and adopted.

1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable outlines the Dissemination and Communication Plan to be implemented by the LCA4Bio project. LCA4Bio is committed to developing robust assessment methodologies to certify Bio-based Systems (BbS) and accurately compare the environmental impacts of emerging bio-based technologies with existing systems. This includes consideration for up-scaling and future scenarios using Integrated Assessment Models (IAM) while managing uncertainty effectively.

This is part of Task 7.1 Communication & dissemination plan which specifies that a detailed Dissemination and Communication Plan will be produced at the beginning of the project (M6), based on the preliminary indications given in Annex 1 GA (part B, section 2.2) and in collaboration with the consortium.

1.1 Context of WP7

The aim of this Work Package (WP) is to ensure the transfer of the project outcomes to specific audiences who play various roles: the exploitation of the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) by stakeholders in the bio-based industry; carrying out dissemination actions that will also facilitate replication of knowledge on LCA frameworks identified. The identification of audiences and the establishment of a cooperation strategy with the European Commission, as well as other related projects and initiatives, are vital steps.

1.2 Objectives

The Grant Agreement (GA) contemplates that a detailed Dissemination and Communication Strategy will be produced at the beginning of the project (M6), based on the preliminary indications given in Section 2.2 and collaboration with the consortium. A strong interaction is foreseen with T7.3 and T7.5 on stakeholder identification and engagement. CTA will oversee the execution of various dissemination and communication activities as outlined in the tables of Section 2.2. At a scientific level, each partner will assume responsibility for attending, participating in, and, when applicable, organizing specific scientific events and publications.

The primary goal of the dissemination strategy for LCA4BIO is to develop guidelines and a plan aimed at engaging its key stakeholders and improving its promotion. LCA4BIO will employ a multistep and multichannel approach in its dissemination strategy to effectively reach and engage various stakeholders and target groups. Information will be tailored to meet the specific needs and interests of each group.

This strategy contributes towards achieving the project's specific objectives by ensuring that communication activities effectively inform and promote the LCA4BIO project and its outcomes to diverse audiences, including the media and the general public. It aims to showcase how EU funding plays a crucial role in addressing societal challenges.

The Communication Plan will focus on the following goals:

- (1) Raising awareness and promoting the project's activities and results through a combination of online and offline tools, networking, events, and media outreach.
- (2) Securing high visibility within and beyond the scientific community and engaging political stakeholders at various levels to facilitate broad dissemination of project outcomes.
- (3) Fostering synergies and forging new collaborations with external entities, such as EU platforms, institutions, and regulatory bodies, to amplify the project's impact.

1.3 Management of Communication and Dissemination Activities

To ensure dissemination and communication activities are planned effectively to ensure the project results and activities are communicated on time, the management of communication and dissemination activities in the LCA4BIO project will be set up carefully. CTA will be coordinating all the communication and dissemination activities of this project, focusing on the input and collaboration of all the other consortium members.

1.3.1 Coordination and Implementation Procedures

CTA will establish a structured process to oversee each of these tasks, which includes outlining standard operating procedures for specific tasks:

1. **External Communication Management:** Develop detailed operating procedures for communicating with external stakeholders, including the development and sharing of press releases, newsletters, and other communication materials. This will ensure that project goals, activities, and achievements are communicated in a consistent and organized fashion to external audiences.
2. **Review and Approval of Materials:** Develop a process to review all information and dissemination materials in order to ensure it meets the highest standard of quality, reliability, and accuracy. All materials will have

to be reviewed by CTA and subject-matter-experts of the consortium as well.

3. **Event Participation Reporting:** Create protocols for documenting and disseminating the consortium member’s participation in applicable activities (such as a seminar, workshop, conferences) through disparate modes. As an example, that might involve creating presentations, promotional materials and consolidating event results.

1.3.2 Tracking and Monitoring Partner Activities

The success of our communication and dissemination plan will require a clear and reliable tracking process. We plan to employ the following tracking process:

1. **Activity Logs:** Every single person assigned with an objective will keep detailed logs of all his communication and dissemination activities; The documentation should describe what type of activity was performed, when it occurred (date, location), who the target audience was or attendees were; which materials/equipment if any were used and whether immediate positive effects or feedbacks/deltas were identified.
2. **Updates:** Regular updates from each partner on their activities. The CTA communications lead can curate such updates and send them a few times per semester. “As further work is completed or we adjust our planning based on new information, I’ll continue to provide regular updates here,” the mayor wrote.
3. **Performance metrics:** Determine appropriate KPIs to evaluate the effectiveness of communication initiatives launched by us. KPI data should be a mix of quantitative and some qualitative as well (e.g., range of events, materials provided; quantity of stakeholder involvement).

2 TARGET AUDIENCE

In order to optimize the impact of dissemination, communication, and exploitation efforts within the LCA4BIO project, it is essential to customize key messages and actions according to the diverse target audiences. This involves considering factors such as their level of expertise or knowledge, geographical location, language preferences, socio-cultural background, and other relevant aspects.

The LCA4BIO project targets professionals in the bio-based industry sector as its primary audience members, alongside stakeholders from sectors interested in enhancing environmental performance (such as governmental institutions). This encompasses governmental institutions, policymakers, trade and certification bodies, the scientific community (such as LCA practitioners, bio-engineers, academia, and research groups), as well as end users including bio-based industry companies, specialized consulting firms, and industry associations (e.g., BIC). Additionally, sustainability associations and platforms (e.g., European Platform on LCA | EPLCA; European Bioeconomy Alliance, EUBIA, Cefic, BioChem Europe, CEPE), consumers' organizations, and citizens are also targeted. These groups possess the expertise and influence to make decisions that can enhance environmental performance and effectively utilize new methodologies introduced by the project.

Table 1. Target groups for LCA4Bio results

Stakeholder category	Description
Key	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industrial bio-based sustainability representatives.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific community working on LCA and sustainability. • LCA specialized consulting firms • Other related EU projects (e.g., CALIMERO project)
Multiplicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bio-based industry branch organizations such as BBI JU (Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking), European Bioplastics, and CEPI (Confederation of European Paper Industries). • LCA organizations such as the European Platform on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and the Joint Research Centre (JRC)
Facilitators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialised media • Standardisation bodies • National and EU policy makers • NGOs interested in sustainability

In addition to these groups, the LCA4BIO project is also reaching out to stakeholders within the LCA community, forming a collaborative network of experts who can be engaged for activities based on their specialized expertise.

3 KEY MESSAGES

The LCA4BIO project aims to disseminate its results to relevant stakeholders, including those in the bioeconomy, bio-based industry, LCA-focused entities, research institutions, academia, investors, consumer organizations, and citizens.

Through tailored communication and outreach activities, the project seeks to transfer knowledge on innovative solutions and promote their positive impacts. The dissemination strategy, aligned with Horizon Europe guidelines, will ensure the widespread adoption of commercially attractive and applicable guidelines for bio-based product certification and prospective LCA evaluation of emerging technologies. Key messages will focus on project achievements, with regular updates provided to stakeholders. Effective dissemination will ensure broad access to project outputs, fostering uptake and collaboration while contributing to knowledge building and best practices diffusion.

Table 2. Key Messages for LCA4Bio project

Stakeholder category	Description
Key stakeholders Multiplicators	Scientific side <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a harmonized and improved methodology for assessing the life cycle environmental sustainability and circularity of both high- and low-TRL BbS within the LCA4BIO project. • Enhancement of prospective LCA methodologies to evaluate low-TRL technologies, addressing key challenges to enable fair comparison of environmental impacts between low- and high-TRL systems in future scenarios. • Exploration of potential socio-economic trade-offs, synergies, and substitution effects resulting from the growth of the bioeconomy.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Testing and validation of enhanced methodologies across various use cases of low-TRL emerging bio-based technologies and high-TRL bio-based systems within the LCA4BIO project. <p>Economic side</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction of a practical approach to potentially reduce LCA costs within the bio-based industry. • Identification of opportunities for environmental performance improvements in the five bio-based sectors targeted by LCA4BIO.
<p>Facilitators</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a methodology to align the Product's Environmental Footprint with the European Commission's green claim strategy. • Anticipation of potential impacts on environmental, economic, and technological fronts for both society and industries. • Recognition of bio-based solutions as a significant opportunity to advance green claims further.

In addition to these scientific and economic advancements, the LCA4BIO project will also design and implement dissemination and communication strategies to generate global interest in the bio-based sector and accelerate the implementation of project results.

4 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The primary goal of the LCA4BIO project's dissemination strategy is to generate interest among pertinent stakeholders by forming inclusive stakeholder groups encompassing various maturity levels and sectors, notably within the bioeconomy. This approach aims to engage bio-based industry companies, LCA-focused entities, research institutions, academia, potential investors, consumer organizations, and citizens. Through exploitation-oriented dissemination, the project seeks to facilitate knowledge transfer regarding its innovative solutions and highlight the positive impacts of these solutions.

The dissemination plan will progress through three phases, each adapting to the evolution of LCA4BIO:

1. **Awareness Phase (M1-M12):** During this initial stage, priority will be given to establishing a community of stakeholders and selecting suitable channels for dissemination. Activities will be conducted to raise awareness about the LCA4BIO project and its objectives among key groups, including industry representatives, academic institutions, governmental bodies, and other relevant stakeholders. Efforts will be made to identify the most effective communication channels and build strong relationships with these stakeholders from the outset.
2. **Scientific Cooperation Phase (M6-M36):** During this phase, the focus will be on fostering cooperation with similar projects and initiatives and ensuring that research findings are made available to specific audiences. Activities such as participation in conferences, publication of articles in relevant scientific journals, and organization of workshops and events will be carried out to share knowledge and collaborate with the scientific community in the fields of life cycle assessment (LCA) and bioeconomy. Additionally, links will be established with professional associations and networks to maximize the impact and dissemination of

project results.

3. **Exploitation-Focused Phase (M24-M36):** In this advanced stage of the project, particular emphasis will be placed on supporting the actual exploitation of results by target users. This will involve activities such as developing marketing plans and identifying knowledge transfer opportunities to ensure that project outcomes are effectively implemented in practice. Additional efforts will be made to engage end users and ensure that project results meet their needs and expectations. Furthermore, opportunities will be sought to showcase project achievements at high-profile events and establish strategic partnerships with key stakeholders in the field of bioeconomy and life cycle assessment.

Table 3. Dissemination activities of LCA4Bio

Tool/Channel	Stakeholder category	KPIs	Target
Brochure & leaflets	All	Nº. Brochures	500 downloaded
Project Website	All	Nº. Visits	800 per year
Social media (Twitter, LinkedIn and Youtube)	Key stakeholders, Multiplicators	Nº. Followers Engagement rate	500 followers 0.6%
Videos	Key stakeholders, Multiplicators	Nº. Project Videos Nº. Views	2 videos 300 views
Newsletter	Key stakeholders, Multiplicators	Nº. Newsletters per year % of opening rate Subscribers	2 per year 1.7% opening rate 300 subscribers
Press Releases	Multiplicators	Nº of Press Releases	4 press releases
Scientific Publications	All	Nº. Publications	12
Training workshops	Key stakeholders, Multiplicators	Nº. Webinars Nº. Attendees	4 15 – 25 attendees
Co-Creation workshops	Key stakeholders, Multiplicators	Nº. of online workshops	5
Conferences and events	Key stakeholders, Multiplicators	Nº. Conferences attended. Nº. Project presentation	15 10
Trade Fairs	Key stakeholders, Multiplicators	Nº. Trade Fairs attended	6

The difference between the figures included in the Grant Agreement (GA) and those reported in the KPI table arises from a reassessment of the project's communication and dissemination potential after its launch.

Regarding **scientific publications**, the initial target of “ ≥ 12 publications” was considered ambitious given the project's scope and the expected timing of scientific outputs. While the consortium aims to reach this figure, most publications will likely be finalized towards the end of the project or shortly after its completion, due to the complexity of the research activities and the time required for peer review and publication processes.

Concerning conference presentations, the number has been increased from 9 to 15. After reviewing the dissemination opportunities available throughout the three-year duration, the consortium concluded that a higher figure better reflects the project's potential to actively engage with relevant scientific and industrial communities.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This target is both achievable and aligned with the consortium's proactive participation in events across Europe.

The LCA4BIO project is adopting an "Open Access" (OA) approach, which is crucial for promoting open collaboration, sharing tools, and disseminating knowledge effectively. This approach is reflected in the dissemination plan through the following actions:

4.1 Open-access Scientific Publications

Implementing an open access (OA) policy for peer-reviewed papers offers multiple benefits. It promotes transparency in the research process, fosters opportunities for collaboration within the scientific community, and enhances research efficiency by enabling sharing, reproduction, and replication of findings. The project aims to publish approximately 6 peer-reviewed scientific papers with completion by ongoing impact measured by citation counts.

The commitment towards OA is illustrated through active participation from LCA4BIO consortium involving partners who are committed to advancing LCA methodologies and sustainability promotions in specific bio-based industries.

II. Policy feedback: Providing feedback to policymakers based on LCA4Bio project outcomes and research findings to inform the development of policies related to the bio-based industry and environmental sustainability.

III. Cooperation strategy: LCA4Bio will build synergies with other projects funded under Horizon Europe, notably under the same topic as well as with other relevant ongoing or future projects to maximize the impact of research efforts. Additionally, close ties will be established with previous BBI JU-funded projects focused on bio-based industries and with the Joint Research Centre (JRC), which oversees EU activities related to the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) system. These collaborations aim to enhance synergies and maximize the impact of LCA4BIO within the broader bio-based industry landscape.

IV. Stakeholder management and engagement: Engaging stakeholders at different levels such as including industry representatives, policymakers, research institutions, and the public, to ensure their involvement in project activities and to gather feedback on project progress and outcomes. This includes organizing stakeholder meetings, workshops, and events to facilitate dialogue and collaboration.

5 TOOLS AND CHANNELS

The current and upcoming communication activities are both aimed at well communicating the project aims and outcomes to a range of audience in plain English. Under the lead of CTA, and support of the consortium, a consistent communication strategy is put in place. This strategy will be built on a comprehensive set of methods and tools that showcase the success and high relevance of the project, and how the project operates in a comprehensible manner for an audience.

By using the broad range of communication possibilities, the project consortium will raise awareness and understanding of how research and innovation within the LCA4BIO project can contribute to addressing the sustainability challenges and improving the environmental performance of the bio-based products and systems in the European Union.

They will also explain and show the societal benefits of innovative LCA based environmental impact assessment methodologies and increase the visibility and awareness of the pivotal role of Horizon Europe and EU-funded research in driving and delivering on ambitious EU goals.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The strategy of LCA4BIO will ensure that its communication plan is revised on a regular basis and aligned with the changing needs and future outlook. Key elements of the strategic communication plan include:

- Development of a visual identity, including a project logo, slogan, and brand for all communication materials.
- Operation of a dedicated website, accessible throughout the project duration and for a period after its completion.
- Utilization of social media platforms such as LinkedIn, Twitter and Youtube, initiated early in the project timeline.
- Distribution of biannual newsletters, providing updates every six months.
- Issuance of press releases and relevant materials, including a media kit, to engage with media outlets and journalists.
- Participation and presentation of project outcomes at innovation events, networking opportunities, and industry exhibitions.
- Engagement with external networks and groups beyond the project's direct scope, leveraging consortium partners' existing connections.
- Delivery of in-house presentations to current collaborators, fostering discussions on potential applications and expansions of LCA4BIO results within various sectors of the bio-based industries.

In addition to the aforementioned strategies, tailored materials such as brochures, case studies, stories, and documents, supplemented with audio-visual content and testimonials, will be developed to engage the general public. Furthermore, media relations will be cultivated to involve journalists and bloggers in the dissemination of the project's updates through social media releases.

According to Article 17 of the GA, any communication activity and publication part of the project, including the project website, must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement. The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands, or text.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos. Furthermore, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

For LCA4Bio, the grant number has also been added to the funding statement.

Funded by
the European Union

Figure 1. European flag and funding statement

Inside WP7, Task 7.5 Clustering and coordination with projects marks the importance of structuring collaboration with other European projects and the agreement on a cooperation structure.

LCA4Bio project will set a collaborative approach with other EU-related initiatives such as CALIMERO, ALIGNED and ESCIB among other organisations to boost and maximise the impacts on the different tools and channels.

5.1 Project Identity

A distinctive project identity has been established to establish a visual brand presence. This identity comprises a set of templates designed to enhance project visibility over time. It encompasses the creation of a project logo and a comprehensive style guide. These components are applied uniformly across different communication materials, including the project website, PowerPoint presentations, Word documents, posters, and reports.

LCA4bio LCA4bio

CORPORATE TYPOGRAPHY

**PRIMARY FONT
KANIT**

**DESIGNER :
CADSON DEMAK**

THE FONT

Kanit means mathematics in Thai, and the Kanit typeface family is a formal Loopless Thai and Sans Latin design. It is a combination of concepts, mixing a Humanist Sans Serif motif with the curves of Capsulated Geometric styles that makes it suitable for various uses, contemporary and futuristic. A notable detail is that the stroke terminals have flat angles, which allows the design to enjoy decreased spacing between letters while preserving readability and legibility at smaller point sizes.

**TYPE EXAMPLES
KANIT**

KANIT

Bold	A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z
Regular	A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z
Figures	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0
Special Characters	! " \$ % & / () = ? ` ; : i " ¶ c [] { } * ¨ ' ¸ « » € ® † Ω " / ø π • ± ' ¨ æ œ @ Δ ° º © ¢ £ ¤ ¥ ¦ § ¨ √ ~ μ ∞ ... - ≤ > ≥ √ < ∅

Basic use guide for logo LCA4BIO EU PROJECT

Figure 2. LCA4Bio Brand guidelines.

5.2 Project Website

LCA4BIO has meticulously developed and consistently maintains its dedicated website, accessible at www.lca4bio.eu. The procurement of the URL was diligently undertaken at the project's onset, precisely on April 1, 2024, with a commitment to its sustained availability throughout the project's lifecycle and for an additional two-year period subsequent to its culmination.

The LCA4BIO project website will function as the primary platform for disseminating external information, providing regular updates to all target audiences regarding project activities and achievements. The main objective is to present the progress and achievements of the project to wider audience comprising members of the public, stakeholders, and industry players.

The website will serve as the central hub for all communication efforts and social media activities conducted by project partners. The strategy for increasing traffic on our site includes creating backlinks between our partner websites and other related online platforms; we exchange information with high visibility. Each project partner will contribute relevant project information to ensure comprehensive coverage and engagement on the website.

The project website contains:

- About section regarding the objectives, impacts and methodology of the project.
- Results (Deliverables, Scientific Publications).
- Resources (newsletter, documents, articles).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

- Latest news about the project progress and results.
- Contact information.
- Details about the consortium partners.
- The project's videos once developed.

Figure 3. LCA4Bio project website.

As necessary, CTA has integrated pop-ups to promote various engagement activities, including workshops, surveys, and more.

The website is optimized for various screen sizes and device types, ensuring compatibility with smartphones and tablets. Visitor data will be collected and analysed using Metricool, with insights integrated into project reports. Metricool's visual reporting capabilities will provide a visually appealing summary of this information.

5.3 Content Management System

The project coordinators, CTA, have selected Microsoft Teams and SharePoint as the designated software solutions for facilitating remote collaboration and content management within the consortium. Under this arrangement, CTA has instituted the SharePoint and Teams group, which serves as the central repository for internal project documentation. Access to this online platform is extended to all project partners and pertinent stakeholders, enabling secure sharing of relevant information, encompassing technical specifications, confidential deliverables, and preliminary project findings.

This repository functions as a platform for consortium members to store, exchange, and collaboratively edit files online, facilitating seamless document creation. Online meetings within the project will primarily be conducted through Microsoft Teams, complemented by material sharing via email for internal communication among LCA4Bio partners.

Additionally, the consortium's internal communication channels feature a dissemination table structured to ensure uniform reporting across all consortium members. This table includes the following categories: Partner,

Communication Activity Name, Description, Target Audience, Communication Channel, Outcome Status, Relevant Link, Date, and Project Month.

5.4 Social Media

The LCA4Bio project maintains an active social media presence on Twitter (https://twitter.com/LCA4Bio_project), LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/lca4bio-project/>) to ensure broader dissemination across different age groups and target audiences. Additionally, a YouTube channel will be established to upload the project's first video, which will then be embedded on the project website.

Since the project's kick-off meeting, content has been regularly posted on social media platforms, with updates occurring at least once a week to enhance outreach. The primary objective of utilizing social media is to drive traffic to the project website while also sharing project-related materials, achievements, events, and other relevant initiatives.

To establish an audience for future project outcomes and events involving stakeholders, Contactica has been managing the social media accounts during this initial project phase. Posts are regularly published to these accounts, covering topics related to the project's scope, objectives, attended events, and information about relevant projects.

Online media channels are monitored to gather analytics data on sources, content types, and individuals or organizations supporting or sharing project messaging. This data will inform targeted communication efforts to maximize the reach of project news and outcomes. Both the final dissemination report and interim reports will incorporate these findings. Contactica oversees the management of social media profiles, with support from partners who are encouraged to follow the project's online presence and engage with its content whenever possible.

Until this document, the LCA4Bio project Social Media figures are:

Table 4. Social Media Profiles of LCA4Bio

KPI	Linkedin	Twitter
Post	12	9
Followers	136	18
Impressions	4.906	274
Interactions	592	20
Engagement Rate	6,03%	1,5%

Here are some best practices to optimize partners' efforts on social media for the LCA4BIO project:

- Tag the project networks in relevant posts:
 - Twitter: @LCA4BIO_project
 - LinkedIn: LCA4BIO Project
- Tag the European Commission (EC) and the European Research Executive Agency (REA):
 - Twitter: @EU_Commission / @REA_research

- LinkedIn: European Commission / European Research Executive Agency (REA)
- Tag related projects and initiatives, such as Calimero, ALIGNED, and ESCIB:
 - Twitter: @CALIMERO_HE / @ALIGNED_HE / @ @ESCIB
 - LinkedIn: CALIMERO HE Project / ALIGNED project / ESCIB Project
 - Include relevant hashtags like #bioeconomy, #innovation, #LCA in the posts.
 - Add a call to action prompting users to visit the project website by providing the link (e.g., "Visit our website to learn more about this" or "More information on our website").
 - Keep track of all communication efforts using a dissemination table accessible to all partners via Teams.
 - A compilation of pertinent achievements deemed suitable for communication purposes has been outlined below:
 - Press release.
 - The project website is up and running.
 - Stakeholders' list.
 - Subscribe to our newsletter.
 - Promotional materials.
 - Conferences & events attended.
 - Newsletters.
 - Training workshops.
 - Sector engagement workshops.
 - Related projects.
 - Case study final modelling results.
 - Video.
 - Scientific publications.
 - General Assembly meetings.
 - Final event.
 - Participation in the Horizon results booster initiative.

5.5 Printed and Digital Materials

Brochures, posters, and factsheets have been crafted for dissemination within partner networks and at various events such as conferences, exhibitions, workshops, and training sessions. These materials provide comprehensive details about the project's activities, participants, and anticipated outcomes.

LCA4bio
Harmonised Life Cycle Assessment methods for sustainable and circular BIO-based systems

REALISTIC ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT OF BIO-BASED SYSTEM TO FACILITATE THE GREEN TRANSITION OF THE EUROPEAN INDUSTRY

LCA4BIO is a pioneering project aimed at developing and validating a new suite of enhanced, standardized, and precise methodologies tailored for assessing environmental impacts and circularity within bio-based systems.

These methodologies will be instrumental in facilitating the green transition of the European industry by providing practical tools to evaluate the sustainability performance of bio-based products.

LCA4BIO will lead the development of assessment methodologies to properly evaluate environmental impacts and circularity, that can be applied in certification schemes in mature bio-based Systems and will address the development of new prospective life cycle assessment methodologies, considering up-scaling and future scenarios for emerging bio-based Systems

CONSORTIUM

AALBORG UNIVERSITY | BIOECONOMY FOR CHANGE
LUXEMBOURG INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY | LIST | PEFC
icontactica innovation | INSA | INSTITUT NATIONAL DES SCIENCES APPLIQUES TOULOUSE
NTNU - Trondheim Norwegian University of Science and Technology | cese for | SONAE ARAUCO

OBJECTIVES

- Develop enhanced methodologies for assessing environmental impacts and circularity in bio-based systems.
- Validate the reliability and precision of the developed assessment tools.
- Facilitate the green transition of European industries by providing practical sustainability evaluation methods for bio-based products.
- Address prospective life cycle assessment methodologies, considering upscaling and future scenarios.
- Foster collaboration among stakeholders in the bioeconomy value chain to ensure the adequacy and applicability of the developed methodologies.

www.lca4bioproject.eu | LCA4BIO Project | @LCA4Bio_project

Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation

Project funded by the European Union with the number 101135371. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union.

Figure 4. LCA4Bio project poster

LCA4bio

LCA4BIO aims to enhance sustainability in industrial bio-based systems

To facilitate the understanding of potential socio-economic trade-offs, synergies and substitution effects

To develop of prospective LCA methodologies for emerging bio-based technologies

To develop precise and reliable assessment methodologies to enable the certification of Bbs

The **LCA4BIO** project makes a substantial contribution towards achieving a more sustainable industrial bioeconomy within the framework of the European Green Deal

Follow us on Social Media

[in](#) LCA4BIO Project [@LCA4Bio_project](#)

10 Members from 7 Countries

- Universities
- Research Institutes
- Certifiers
- Industrial Companies

Funded by the European Union

Project funded by the European Union with the number 101135371. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union.

Figure 5. LCA4Bio project factsheet.

Impact

LCA4BIO is a pioneering project aimed at developing and validating a new suite of enhanced, standardized, and precise methodologies tailored for assessing environmental impacts and circularity within bio-based systems.

These methodologies will be instrumental in facilitating the green transition of the European industry by providing practical tools to evaluate the sustainability performance of bio-based products.

LCA4BIO will lead the development of assessment methodologies to properly evaluate environmental impacts and circularity, that can be applied in certification schemes in mature bio-based Systems and will address the development of new prospective life cycle assessment methodologies, considering up-scaling and future scenarios for emerging bio-based Systems.

The substitution of fossil-based technologies by bio-based ones

Development of sustainability and circularity criteria, and its implementation in new guidelines and certification for bio-based products to demonstrate the sustainability of their activities and circularity of the materials involved in their production

Improved prospective LCA methodologies will be developed, based on novel IAMs that will use manageable levels of uncertainty

Funded by the European Union | WWW.LCA4BIO-PROJECT.EU

LCA4bio

Fossil resource depletion and environmental impacts underscore the urgency for change.

PROJECT PARTNERS

AALBORG UNIVERSITY, INSA, LIST, CESA FOR, CONTACTICA, PEFC, NTNU - Trondheim, SONAE ARAUCO

Scan site web LCA4BIO project | Get in touch with us for further information: nuria.valdes@contactica.es

LCA4bio

Life Cycle Assessment methods for sustainable and circular BIO based systems

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (EREA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

LCA4bio Objectives

The main objectives for the LCA4BIO project are focused on pioneering advancements in environmental assessment methodologies tailored specifically for bio-based systems. Our primary goals include:

- Develop enhanced methodologies for assessing environmental impacts and circularity in bio-based systems.
- Validate the reliability and precision of the developed assessment tools.
- Facilitate the green transition of European industries by providing practical sustainability evaluation methods for bio-based products.
- Address prospective life cycle assessment methodologies, considering upscaling and future scenarios.
- Foster collaboration among stakeholders in the bioeconomy value chain to ensure the adequacy and applicability of the developed methodologies.

As the EU's Climate Target Plan drives industries

As the EU's Climate Target Plan drives industries towards drastic reductions in greenhouse gas emissions, the shift from fossil-based to bio-based systems becomes imperative. Fossil resource depletion and environmental impacts underscore the urgency for change.

In response to this call, LCA4BIO spearheads the development of advanced methodologies for environmental assessment in bio-based systems. LCA4BIO goal is to provide precise, reliable, and harmonized evaluation tools that demonstrate the superior performance of bio-based products. By identifying the best available technologies, we pave the way for sustainable industrial practices, aligning with the European Commission's zero-pollution objectives.

Work Packages

- WP 1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT
- WP 2: IMPROVED METHODOLOGIES FOR ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY AND CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT OF BIO-BASED SYSTEMS (BBS)
- WP 3: IMPROVED PROSPECTIVE LCA (ECLA) METHODOLOGY FOR LOW-TRL BIO-BASED TECHNOLOGIES
- WP 4: TRADE- VALIDATION AND TESTING OF DEVELOPED LCA
- WP 5: METHODOLOGIES OFFS AND SYNERGIES CAUSED BY THE GROWTH OF BIO-BASED SYSTEMS
- WP 6: ENSURING THE APPLICABILITY OF LCA METHODOLOGIES TO ALLOW CERTIFICATION OF BBS AND ASSES THE ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE OF LOW-TRL BBS
- WP 7: COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION

LCA4BIO project Life Cycle Assessment methods for sustainable and circular BIO based systems

Follow the project | @LCA4Bio_project | LCA4Bio Project

Figure 6. LCA4Bio project brochure.

Additionally, a single PowerPoint presentation model has been developed to cater to various needs:

- The first one incorporate details about the project's work package structure and case studies. This version is intended for presentations to other European projects or initiatives, as well as groups familiar with the structure of Horizon Europe projects.
- The second one, shared internally within the consortium, serves as a supportive resource for presentations at trade fairs, conferences, and other events.

5.6 Newsletters

A regular electronic newsletter will be prepared every six months, including project updates, news, interviews and other content about LCA4BIO and distributed to stakeholders and partner networks. The contents will also be shared on the project's website and may be included in the newsletters that partner organizations send out to their contacts in the relevant industries.

To create a recipients' list, an invitation to subscribe to the newsletter has been published on social media and the project's website. Individuals who are included in the list of stakeholders and have given us their consent have also been included, in compliance with GDPR. No personal information is used without consent. The service provider selected for the newsletter is Mailchimp.

5.7 Press Releases

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Press releases will be created to report important events of the progress of this project as they happen. Partners will be urged to translate and disseminate the press releases to local and national media in their country. Press releases will be written in English. Initially drafted in English, press releases will be distributed to European press and English-speaking journalists, prioritizing news agencies as primary sources for major media outlets and newspapers.

The inaugural press release, which includes information about the project kick-off meeting, has already been circulated. Additionally, the first press release, containing details about the project, was sent to partners for distribution alongside the kick-off meeting announcement.

5.8 Scientific Publications

The scientific publications of the LCA4BIO project will be disseminated to different target groups, including the scientific community, education, industry, and policy makers, highlighting scientific excellence and research achievements. It is expected that 6 peer-reviewed scientific papers will be published by the closing of the project. After the project, the impact will be further measured by citation scores.

5.9 Participation in Conferences, Workshops, and Events

The consortium partners will engage in presenting the LCA4BIO project and its outcomes at innovation and networking events, technological fairs, and exhibitions. Additionally, they will disseminate project information within other networks and groups, leveraging their existing strong connections and involvement, even if these are not directly associated with the project.

5.10 Stakeholder Engagement

The project's effectiveness in achieving its objectives relies on the active engagement of stakeholders from the project's inception. A comprehensive list of stakeholders is currently being developed collaboratively by all partners, initiated from M1. These stakeholders will receive regular updates on project developments, events, and outcomes through newsletters and direct communication.

Drawing upon their expertise, stakeholders will be invited to participate in various activities, including training workshops aimed at gathering feedback on environmental impact assessment perspectives within the sector.

6 INDICATORS AND TARGETS

The attainment of defined targets outlined in Table 3 will serve as the benchmark for evaluating the successful implementation of the Dissemination and Communication Plan upon the project's conclusion.

7 LEVELS OF COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION

The choice of communication methods and media will be tailored to accommodate the diverse geographic reach of key target groups.

7.1 European Level – European Commission

Regular updates on project outcomes will be provided to the European Commission through periodic reporting, including the mid-term review and updates to project documentation. Collaboration opportunities with other ongoing projects for dissemination activities will be explored, and adjustments to current work will be proposed as Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

necessary.

7.2 International Level – Industry, Scientific Community

Relevant international organizations will be informed about the project's findings. Scientific insights will be translated into practical data, regulations, and recommendations. Electronic resources will be directly shared with designated organizations and stakeholders to raise public awareness.

Technical publications, conferences, and workshops, both nationally and internationally, as well as industry meetings and participation in industrial forums, will be utilized to disseminate knowledge to both research and industrial audiences.

8 METHODOLOGY

The following internal and external communication actions will be carried out throughout the LCA4BIO project and beyond, ensuring successful and efficient dissemination of outcomes to project partners, stakeholders, and broader audiences.

8.1 Internal Communication

Effective internal communication is essential for information sharing and goal achievement. This is facilitated through regular meetings, conference calls and consortium meetings. Microsoft Teams is utilized to enhance collaboration among project partners. The project's communication and dissemination plan will be periodically updated with input from partners, and project materials are shared on a dedicated Microsoft SharePoint space for internal use. This space contains updates on project progress, meeting documents, and project reports, accessible via login credentials.

8.2 External Communication

The LCA4BIO project team uses a variety of platforms to publicize its work, including as journals, conferences, trade exhibitions, workshops, industry associations, and the media. The findings of the project will be published in reports, articles, and publications. Public access to all scientific publications and public communications will be encouraged within the scientific community.

9 TIMELINE: ACTIONS IN M1 – M6

During the initial stages of the project, our focus was on raising awareness of the LCA4BIO project's objectives and disseminating emerging results. Collaborating closely with the project partners, CTA curated essential information and shared it through accessible articles on our project website. Concurrently, we leveraged social media platforms to drive traffic to the website and amplify our outreach efforts.

As we advance through the project timeline, our communication and dissemination strategies will evolve in tandem with our project milestones and deliverables. Social media updates will be synchronized with our website to ensure a cohesive information flow and drive engagement. We will strategically intensify our communication efforts during key project events, including workshops, the release of research findings, and project launches. Together with our consortium partners, CTA remains committed to maintaining the visibility and impact of the LCA4BIO project through regular updates, targeted events, and ongoing engagement activities.

9.1 Project identity and Materials

At the outset of the project, CTA spearheaded the development of a visual identity for LCA4BIO, which encompassed the creation of the project logo and comprehensive guidelines for brand elements such as typography, colours, and style. Additionally, a suite of communication materials was crafted, including a brochure, roll-up banner, poster, and project presentations. Templates for deliverables, including Word documents and PowerPoint templates, were also meticulously designed, and shared with our consortium partners.

The initial set of communication materials, including a brochure, poster, fact sheet, roll-up banner, and project presentation, has been meticulously created and made available for access on the project's website. Moving forward, these materials will be continuously updated and uploaded to the website as they are developed over the course of the project.

Project funded by the European Union with the number 101135371. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union.

Figure 7. LCA4Bio project Word Template.

9.2 Press Release

The initiative began with the launch of a press release, which was distributed by CTA and various consortium partners to numerous local and trade media outlets.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

LCA4Bio: Pioneering European Project Aims to Propel Green Transition in Industry

- *LCA4Bio, a 36-months European initiative with ten partners from seven countries, is at the forefront of addressing the European Union's Climate Target Plan by developing advanced assessment methodologies for bio-based systems.*
- *The ground-breaking project aims to revolutionize environmental assessments, allowing to investigate the performance of bio-based products compared to fossil alternatives*

Madrid, Spain. 11 April 2024 - The European Union's ambitious Climate Target Plan has set a formidable mandate for all economic sectors to dramatically reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Responding to this imperative, the LCA4Bio project emerges as a new initiative geared towards facilitating the green transition of the European industry.

The global imperative to shift from fossil-based feedstocks and processes to bio-based systems gains momentum as the environmental impacts and depletion of fossil resources become increasingly evident. LCA4Bio stands at the forefront, addressing this challenge by developing and validating a new set of improved, harmonized, precise, reliable, and applicable environmental assessment methodologies for bio-based systems.

The primary goal of LCA4Bio is to provide a more applicable and realistic environmental assessment of bio-based systems. This approach will enable to certify the superior performance of bio-based products compared to unsustainable counterparts, aligning with the zero-pollution objectives encouraged by the European Commission. By identifying the best available technologies, LCA4Bio strives to promote sustainability in industrial procedures.

Over the next 36 months, LCA4Bio will bring together a consortium of ten partners from seven different countries, pooling their expertise to pioneer advancements in life cycle assessment methodologies. These methodologies will not only evaluate environmental impacts and circularity in bio-based systems but also serve as a foundation for certification schemes, facilitating the international trade of bio-based products.

Project funded by the European Union with the number 101135371. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union.

Figure 8. LCA4Bio project first press release.

9.3 Website

The website www.lca4bioproject.eu was launched during the fourth month of the project, providing essential project information. It will serve as a dynamic platform continually updated with progress updates and news from project partners. Additionally, all materials developed throughout the project will be regularly uploaded and made accessible on the website.

For the time being, the following statistical data has been obtained, highlighting 15,62% of the visits KPI (125 vs 800 per year) for first year during the M5-M6 period.

9.4 Social Media

On the day of the project's kick-off meeting, social media accounts on LinkedIn and Twitter were launched. Since then, these accounts are updated regularly, with a goal of one post per week. At M5, a total of 21 social media publications have been posted on LinkedIn (12) and Twitter (9), reaching a total of 154 followers (136 on LinkedIn

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

and 18 in Twitter), with more than 4.906 impressions on LinkedIn and 274 on Twitter.

Figure 9. LCA4Bio Project Social Media followers overview (April 2024).

9.5 Newsletter

The first Newsletter was sent in M5 including the general information of the project such as the concept, objectives, partners, and the latest relevant news.

Newsletter Link: <https://bit.ly/3JStyMA>

9.6 Events Attended

Consortium members have already participated in 1 event to promote the LCA4Bio project during the first project semester:

- “Prospective LCA network” online seminar (Thomas Schaubroeck, Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology). February 2024.

9.7 Interaction with other EU Initiatives

A first meeting was conducted in January 2024 to consider potential future activities to carry out jointly between LCA4Bio and its sister project under the same call: CALIMERO and ALIGNED. Apart from this, CTA also contacted

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

the following related initiatives:

- ESCIB project

Apart from CALIMERO and ALIGNED, CTA also discussed with ESCIB project to evaluate the possibility to participate in joint events.

Additionally, the LCA4Bio project will join the European Bioeconomy Network, an alliance of more than 100 projects and initiatives dealing with Bioeconomy promotion, communication, and support. The main goal is to maximise the efforts, increasing knowledge sharing, networking, mutual learning, and coordination of joint activities and events.